

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Realization of the Relationship between Quantum Mechanics and Relativity

Mohamed Daris

Department of Physics, Faculty of Sciences University Rabbat Morocco, Morocco, Rabat

Received: 15-06-2018, Revised: 20-07-2018, Accepted: 10-08-2018

ABSTRACT

Relativity and quantum mechanics remain two very binding things, and both are separating either by method or physical experience. In this section, I will make an approach to better facilitate a connection between quantum mechanics and relativity that gives us a new vision on the fact that the two concepts can be related theoretically and experimentally to give birth to the new principles in the physical theory and to better improve theoretical and experimental research. The new conception of this principle develops scientific and technical research better.

Key words: Energy volume, energy mass, energy density, matter, quantum mechanics, speed of the light, mass

INTRODUCTION

In this section, we will have the design of a central energy model based on the energy of the light E ; this model has three forms of energy: The energy of the mass E_m which is based deep on the mass (m) in relation with the wave function (Ψ), the density energy (E_ρ) which is based on the density (ρ) in relation to the wave function (Ψ), and the volume energy (E_v) which is based on the volume V in relation with the wave function (Ψ). This approximation gives us access; to the important paragraph in this research; is the relationship between quantum mechanics and relativity.

DISCUSSION

Realization of the relationship between quantum mechanics and relativity:^[1-6]

(I) Relationship building for the model (E_m , E_ρ , and E_v):

We have:

$$E = \Psi C^2 \sqrt{T_F};$$

$$m = \frac{E}{C^2 \sqrt{T_F}} = \frac{\Psi C^2 \sqrt{T_F}}{\sqrt{\rho}} \times \frac{1}{C^2 \sqrt{T_F}} = \frac{\Psi}{\sqrt{\rho}}$$

Moreover, we know that: $m = \frac{\Psi}{\sqrt{\rho}}$

$$\text{So: } \rho = \frac{\Psi^2}{m^2}; V = \frac{m}{\rho} = \frac{\Psi}{\sqrt{\rho}} = \frac{m^2}{\Psi^2} = \frac{m^2}{\sqrt{\rho} \Psi}$$

$$m = \frac{\Psi}{\sqrt{\rho}}; \rho = \frac{\Psi^2}{m^2}; V = \frac{m^2}{\sqrt{\rho} \Psi}$$

Model design (E_m , E_ρ , E_v):

We have:

$$m = \frac{E}{C^2 \sqrt{T_F}} = \frac{\Psi}{\sqrt{\rho}}; \rho = \left(\frac{\emptyset c^2}{E} \right)^2 \times T_F = \frac{\emptyset^2}{m^2};$$

$$V = \frac{E}{c^2 \Psi^2 \sqrt{T_F}} = \frac{m^2}{\sqrt{\rho} \Psi}$$

For E_m , we have:

$$\frac{E}{C^2 \sqrt{T_F}} = \frac{\Psi}{\sqrt{\rho}}$$

So:

$$E = \frac{\Psi c^2 \sqrt{T_F}}{\sqrt{\rho}}$$

$$E_m = \Psi c^2 \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Address for Correspondence:

Mohamed daris,

E-mail: Mohamed_aout@hotmail.fr

For E_ρ , we have:

$$\left(\frac{\Psi c^2}{E}\right)^2 \times T_F = \frac{\Psi^2}{m^2}$$

So:

$$\frac{\Psi C^4}{E^2} \times T_F = \frac{\Psi^2}{m^2}$$

$$E_\rho = mc^2 \sqrt{T_F}$$

$$\text{So: } E_\rho = \frac{\Psi}{\sqrt{\rho}} c^2 \sqrt{T_F} = \Psi c^2 \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$E_\rho = \Psi c^2 \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

For E_v , we have:

$$V = \frac{E}{c^2 \Psi^2 \sqrt{T_F}} = \frac{m^2}{\sqrt{\rho} \Psi}$$

$$\text{So: } E = m^2 c^2 \Psi \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\text{So: } E = m^2 c^2 \Psi \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Hence, the three final results are as follows:

$$E_m = \Psi c^2 \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}; E_\rho = \Psi c^2 \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}};$$

$$E_v = m^2 c^2 \Psi \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\text{We can deduce that: } E_m = E_\rho = \Psi c^2 \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\text{Hence, we have: } E_v = E_\rho m^2 = E_m m^2$$

These results show that volume-related energy E_v is very large compared to the energy related to the mass energy E_m or density E_ρ which are identical.

$$\text{We have: } \rho = \frac{\Psi^2}{m^2}$$

$$\text{so: } m^2 = \frac{\Psi^2}{\rho}$$

Hence, we will have the new relationship:

$$E_v = m^2 c^2 \Psi \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\Psi^3 c^2}{\rho} \left(\frac{T_F}{\rho}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\text{So: } E_v = \frac{\Psi^3 c^2 \sqrt{T_F}}{(\rho)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$$

We have:

$$\text{So: } E_v = E_\rho \frac{\Psi^2}{\rho} = E_m \frac{\Psi^2}{\rho}$$

Hence, we have the stability of the total matter:

$$\rho E_v = E_\rho \Psi^2$$

Moreover, we have:

$$\rho E_v = E_m \Psi^2$$

Hence, we have the density of matter which exists in two forms of energy: Mass energy and energy density. In a global form of energy, which is the energy density, we have:

$$\rho = \frac{E_\rho \Psi^2}{E_v} = \frac{E_m \Psi^2}{E_v}$$

This relation is total stable energy equilibrium relation of: matter; body; system; universe... has energy E_m ; E_ρ ; E_v . This relationship represents a link between quantum mechanics and relativity. The final equation of the connection between relativity and quantum mechanics is:

We pose:

$$E_\rho = E_m = E$$

Hence, we will have:

$$\rho = \frac{E \Psi^2}{E_v}$$

Hence, the final equation is this:

$$E = \frac{\rho E_v}{\Psi^2}$$

This equation is the Link between relativity and quantum mechanics which shows that energy

$$E = mc^2 \sqrt{T_F}$$

linked with the wave function Ψ to density ρ in a volumic energy. This result is final for this link.

Physical interpretation of the results exploited:

Energy $E = mc^2 \sqrt{T_F}$ is an exact correction of the

classical light equation: $E=mc^2$; the first equation shows that the photon, light, geomatter as the planets, galaxies, stars, and black holes all depend on the spatial time parameter T_F , and consequently, their energy produced depends on the matter of the mass and the speed of the light produced at the level of this body or this system means that the wave function Ψ depends on quantum mechanics and e relativity at the same time, and it is an essential parameter in the

$$\text{equation: } E = \frac{\rho E_V}{\Psi^2}$$

The density ρ and energy E_V represent the complex state of matter that has energy density E_V and density ρ .

This equation is a proper state of the presence of relativity and quantum mechanics at the same time in any system on the universe or far from the universe.

REFERENCES

1. Laura F, David M. A fundamental relation between supermassive black holes and their host galaxies. *Astrophys J Lett* 2000;539:L9-12.
2. Lloyd S. Ultimate physical limits to computation *Nature* 2000;406:1047-54.
3. Laura F, David M. A fundamental relation between supermassive black holes and their host galaxies. *Astrophys J Lett* 2000;539:L9-12.
4. Gottfried K, Weisskopf VF. The relative permeability and permittivity of field-theoretic vacuums. *Concepts Part Phys* 1986;2:200.
5. Weisskopf VK. *Concepts of Particle Physics*. New York: Oxford University Press; 1986. p. 389.
6. Stirling WJ, Webber BR. *QCD and Collider Physics*. New York: Cambridge University Press; 2003. p. 27-9.